

$$\kappa N_{\kappa}^{(m \pm \lambda)} < m < \kappa(N_{\kappa}^{(m \pm \lambda)} + 1), \kappa = 2, 3, \dots, [(m \pm \lambda)/2]. (*)$$

Obviously, if m is a prime number, then it is sufficient to take $\lambda = 0$. So, to get a contradiction, let us assume that there is a *non-prime* number $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 5$, such that if the numbers $N_2^{(m)}, N_3^{(m)}, \dots, N_{[m/2]}^{(m)} \in \mathbb{N}$ are chosen to satisfy $kN_k^{(m)} \leq m < k(N_k^{(m)} + 1)$ whenever $k = 2, 3, \dots, [m/2]$, then there are *no* $N_2^{(m \pm \lambda)}, N_3^{(m \pm \lambda)}, \dots, N_{[(m \pm \lambda)/2]}^{(m \pm \lambda)} \in \mathbb{N}$ fulfilling inequalities (*) whenever $\lambda \in \{1, 2, \dots, m - 1\}$. Equivalently, this means that, given any $\lambda \in \{1, 2, \dots, m - 1\}$, there is a $n_{\lambda} \in \{2, 3, \dots, [(m \pm \lambda)/2]\}$ such that $n_{\lambda}N_{n_{\lambda}}^{(m \pm \lambda)} = m \pm \lambda$ for some $N_{n_{\lambda}}^{(m \pm \lambda)} \in \mathbb{N}$. In other words, in such a case, there should have been numbers $n_1, \dots, n_{m-1} \in \{2, 3, \dots, [(m \pm \lambda)/2]\}$ such that the corresponding natural numbers $N_{n_{\lambda}}^{(m \pm \lambda)}$ ($\lambda = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$) satisfy the system of equations $n_{\lambda}N_{n_{\lambda}}^{(m \pm \lambda)} = m \pm \lambda, \lambda = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$. In particular, this implies that there would be no prime number between integers m and $2m$ which is impossible to happen by *Bertrand's postulate* ([2, 4]), nor no prime number between integers 1 and $m - 1$ which is also impossible to apply since m is taken to be greater than 5. \square

Corollary (Proof of Goldbach's Conjecture ([1, 3]))

(i). *Every even number greater than 4 can be written as the sum of two primes.*

(ii). *Every odd number greater than 5 can be written as the sum of three primes.*

Proof. (i). Let $2m$ be an even number greater than 4 ($\Rightarrow m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2\}$). From the *Reflective Arrangement of Prime Numbers*, it follows that there is a $\lambda \in \{1, \dots, m - 1\}$ for which both integers $m \pm \lambda$ are positive prime numbers, say $m \pm \lambda = p_{(\pm)} \in \mathbb{N}$. So, we may have $m - \lambda = p_{(-)}$ and $m + \lambda = p_{(+)}$. Adding these equations, we are done.

(ii). Let $2m + 1$ be an odd number greater than 5 ($\Rightarrow m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2\}$). By the first part, there are two positive prime numbers $p_{(-)}$ and $p_{(+)}$ such that $2m + 1 = p_{(-)} + p_{(+)} + 1$. Since $p_{(+)} + 1 = \text{even}$, another application of the first part guarantees that $p_{(+)} + 1 = q_{(-)} + q_{(+)}$ for two positive prime numbers $q_{(-)}$ and $q_{(+)}$. Combination of the last two relationships shows that $2m + 1 = p_{(-)} + q_{(-)} + q_{(+)}$ and thus, the proof is complete. \square

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